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Exploring the Knowledge Structure of the Information Domain (2014-2023) in Five Selected Journals Using Topic Modeling

Abstract

This study explores the knowledge structure of the information domain by analyzing the publication records (n=3,383) of five selected journals obtained from Scopus. BERTopic modeling was used to identify key topics from the abstracts of the publications and their evolution over time. The results reveal popular topics and emerging trends in the field. Most of the topics are aligned with the integration of technology, consumer behavior, AI, organizational innovation, privacy, governance, and social media. Although this study is based on limited journals, it opens room for future research to explore a broader range of journals with more data. The results can be useful for researchers in the field.

Keywords: text mining, k-means clustering, topic representation, emerging research trends, library science

I. Introduction

- The information domain deals with specific types of knowledge and information practices, which vary across academic disciplines, professions, and personal interests [1].
- A knowledge structure is a representation that organizes and makes interconnections between topics or themes within a domain [2], [3].

Research Objectives

- To analyze the publication trends of five selected journals in the information domain from 2014 to 2023.
- To explore the topics within these publications by identifying representative keywords that reflect the current knowledge structure.
- To trace the evolution of these topics within each journal during the said period.

II. Methodology

A. Data Collection

- Five top-ranked journals based on SJR in Library Science (2023)
 - International Journal of Information Management (IJIM), Information Systems Research (ISRE), European Journal of Information Systems (EJIS), Big Data and Society (BDS), Government Information Quarterly (GIQ)
- Total 3,383 records retrieved from Scopus.

B. Dataset Preparation

- Abstracts used as corpus.
- Copyright information removed using Regex.
- Common words (objectives, purposes, etc.) excluded.
- Spelling variations standardized.
- Performed lemmatization.
- Titles used when abstracts were unavailable.

C. Topic Modeling

- Applied BERTopic for topic modeling and k-means clustering [4], [5].
- Used KeyBERTInspired to reduce stopwords [4].
- Re-labeled topics using keywords with ChatGPT. [6]
- Organized and visualized data using Google Sheets, Pandas, and Matplotlib [7], [8].

III. Results and Discussion

A. Publication Trends

Fig.1. Publication trends in five journals (2014-2023)

B. Topic Analysis

TABLE I. TOPICS AND REPRESENTATIVE KEYWORDS IN IJIM

Topic Labels	Representation
Social Marketing and Consumer Behavior	social, marketing, technology, satisfaction, influence, commerce, intention, motivation, consumer, behavior
AI and Organizational Innovation	enterprise, organizational, ai, innovation, management, business, technology, organization, development, develop
Organizational Knowledge Management	organizational, management, knowledge, organization, manage, develop, development, technology, information, innovation
Social Media and Data Protection	twitter, privacy, social, tweet, information, technology, security, platform, disclosure, service
Blockchain and Stakeholder Adoption	blockchain, bitcoin, stakeholder, chain, technology, technological, industry, business, organization, adoption

TABLE II. TOPICS AND REPRESENTATIVE KEYWORDS IN ISRE

Topic Labels	Representation
Market Pricing and Consumer Behavior	market, pricing, advertising, auction, consumer, demand, business, buyer, sale, optimal
Consumer Reviews and Marketing	review, consumer, rating, marketing, quality, product, recommender, purchase, influence, customer
Crowdsourcing and Privacy	crowdsourcing, privacy, influence, crowdfunding, participation, disclosure, peer, community, reward, crowd
Technology and Organizational Behavior	organizational, technology, organization, employee, influence, digital, information, behavior, social, healthcare
Innovation and Strategic Investment	innovation, industry, technology, organizational, investment, strategic, economy, develop, outsourcing, business

Fig.3. Trend of topics in ISRE (2014-2023)

Fig.4. Trend of topics in EJIS (2014-2023)

Fig.5. Trend of topics in BDS (2014-2023)

Fig.6. Trend of topics in GIQ (2014-2023)

TABLE III. TOPICS AND REPRESENTATIVE KEYWORDS IN EJS

Topic Labels	Representation
Strategic Innovation and Organizational Agility	strategic, organizational, business, innovation, technology, develop, management, capability, company, agility
Technology Adoption and User Behavior	continuance, intention, behavior, technology, motivation, trust, perceive, mobile, influence, social
Organizational Security and Privacy Risk	security, privacy, compliance, organizational, threat, risk, policy, information, technology, trust
ICT and Digital Innovation in Organizations	ict, organizational, technology, design, organization, innovation, digital, researcher, develop, social
Conceptual Design and Information Systems	design, artefact, conceptual, develop, development, systems, concept, researcher, information, publication

TABLE IV. TOPICS AND REPRESENTATIVE KEYWORDS IN BDS

Topic Labels	Representation
Surveillance and Digital Privacy	surveillance, privacy, technology, governance, digital, citizen, social, consumer, policy, public
Social Science and Data Knowledge	social, science, technology, data, knowledge, ethnographic, scientist, epistemological, concept, computational
AI and Machine Learning	ai, algorithmic, concept, technology, automate, learning, intelligence, development, machine, moderation
Urban Tech Governance	governance, infrastructure, government, urban, technological, politic, city, political, social, technology
Social Media and Political Discourse	twitter, social, facebook, community, platform, political, public, wikipedia, discourse, web

TABLE V. TOPICS AND REPRESENTATIVE KEYWORDS IN GIQ

Topic Labels	Representation
ICT and Citizen Participation	ict, privacy, participation, citizen, social, government, public, internet, technology, initiative
Innovation and Government Services	innovation, governance, service, government, public, organizational, technology, business, agency, organization
Open Data and Public Accountability	organization, innovation, public, government, participation, ogd, open, policy, accountability, develop
Social Media and Political Communication	social, twitter, facebook, communication, tweet, public, technology, political, government, content
AI and Public Governance	ai, governance, administration, intelligence, technology, policy, public, organization, algorithmic, citizen

IV. Conclusion

- Identified IJIM as the most significant journal.
- Identified five key topics mainly related to integrating technology, consumer behavior, AI, organizational innovation, privacy, governance, and social media.
- Findings suggest how technologies and digital platforms are enhancing public services and business operations.
- Only five journals and three document types selected, covering 10 years.
- Future research could include a broader range of journals.

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